

Effective Management and Academic Achievement: A Study on Leadership Style

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Abstract: Education is the process of enriching learning, or the emergence of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, habits among scholars. Quality education depends on a quality curriculum and the productive management system of the institution. In the world of 21st century, there is a great demand of effective leaders for educational organizations. This paper aims to introduce suitable leadership style for effective educational management and their impact on improving academic achievement. This academic evaluation examines some previously established literature for achieving the research objectives and provides a theoretical understanding of it. This paper begins with a concise overview of Leadership Style, followed by a review of related literature. It depicts that transformational, democratic leadership style has an immense role in efficacious management towards academic excellence. This article also suggests an application of different leadership styles in management based on situational favorableness, diverse work culture and the level of their followers.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Leadership style, Management, Quality Education.

INTRODUCTION

Education is pivotal to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning and furnishing pupils with a high-quality education. It is both the foundation of national growth and a driving force behind sustainable development. Likewise, it is a process by which people acquire information, values, experience, and attitudes. In the world of 21st century, there's a great demand of effective leaders for educational institutions. The effectiveness of leaders in the educational sector is valued by their capabilities to contribute for refining the quality of education in the era of technological advancement (Sungtong, 2007; Abbas et al., 2020). In an educational institution the principle leads the role of a manager or a leader who gives assistance in organizing, directing, supervising the multihued activities inside the institution. According to educational experts, Management is the crucial factor in the growth of both organizations and students' academic performance (Mirkamali, 1995).

In the early years of the 21st century, educational leadership is of immense significance. This is due to the widespread view that leadership effectiveness significantly affects educational development for both students and schools. Many investigators and educationist explained leadership in their own ways, Western (2013) states that leadership is honoured as the competencies and practical expertise of the persons, group or association to lead, influence or to give guidance to other persons, team, or the whole organization. In this way as a leader principal leads the whole organization or provide guidance to the team member for better performance and to achieve organization. Okumbe (1998) describe leadership as a "specific attitude espoused by a leader toward his or her subordinates to motivate them to achieve the organization's objectives and targets." Moreover, different leadership style of a leader influences the work culture in different ways. Bhoomireddy (2004); Goel (2005) and Crum and Sherman (2008) state that a

leader uses different style of leadership considering the situation. Phuc et al (2021) also states that a leadership style refers to a leader's style of giving directions implementing works and motivating followers. Educational leaders use different style for effective management in the organization to upgrade their service quality and academic excellence.

Models of Leadership Style

Black and Mouton Managerial Grid Model: In the early year of 1960s, Robert Black and Jane Mouton developed a "Task vs. Person" oriented leadership model which was also known as 'Leadership Grid' or 'Managerial Grid'. It gives a framework to think about leader's orientation style. This model gives five different leadership styles with a representation of matrix based on the concern for people and the concern for production as –

I. Impoverished leadership style (1,1): Leaders with this style have minimal concern for both people and production at low level.

II. Task Management style (9,1): This type of leaders is more concern about their tasks and organizational production rather than their subordinates.

III. Team Management style (9,9): Leaders with this style are most effective where they have higher level of concern for both people and production.

IV. Country Club style (1,9): This type of leaders is more concern about people or they emphasize more on the needs of the subordinates but have less concern about tasks.

V. Middle of the road style (5,5): It is most applicable leadership style where leaders try to keep balance between both people and production.

Fiedler Contingency Model: In the mid-1960s, Fred Fiedler developed Contingency Model where he states that there is no best style of leadership rather a leader's effectiveness is based on the situations. Fiedler also suggests that a good leader can adjust their leadership style according to the situational demands. These are the result of two factors such as –

I. Leadership style: Fiedler stated that no single style is best but which is suitable with the environment, that is fixed and better. For measuring suitable leadership style, he developed a scale – 'Least Preferred Co-worker (LPC) wherein obtained high score means preferring 'Relationship Oriented style' and low score means 'Task Oriented style'.

II. Situational Favourableness: This factor covers three aspects such as leader-member relationships, task structures and position power or degree of authority.

Hersey and Blanchard Model: Dr. Paul Hersey and Ken Blanchard developed this 'Situational Leadership Theory'. They stated that instead of using one leadership style, a successful leader should change and apply their styles based on the maturity level of followers and the details of task, under which this model gives four leadership style such as –

I. Telling Style (S1): This type of Leadership is mostly task oriented. Where subordinates are not mature enough and have low skill and confidence, a leader can use this type of Leadership style to tell their subordinates exactly what to do and how to do. This leadership style suits Coercive Power to use.

II. Selling Style (S2): Leaders using this style 'sell' their concern for both relationship and task. They provide information as well as direction to the followers and communicate with them. When the followers have medium level of maturity but have limited skills and confidence, at that time a leader can use this type of style with legitimate powers.

III. Participating Style (S3): Where subordinates have medium level of maturity, high level skills but lacking confidence then a leader should apply this type of style with reference type power. These leaders have more focus on the relationship and less focus on direction or production.

IV. Delegating Style (S4): When the followers are highly matured and have skill and confidence in work, a leader can use delegating style with expert power. They are less involved in the teamwork and pass most of the responsibility to the followers.

Tri-Dimensional Model: In the year of 1983, Bill Reddin developed 3D Leadership model to explain the relationship between situational leadership and managerial impact on organizational effectiveness. It's also known as 'Managerial Effectiveness and Style: Individual or Situation'. Reddin's three dimensions are like 1. Task orientation, 2. Relationship orientation and 3. Effectiveness. He also developed four basic styles in 3D Effectiveness as- Related Style, Separated Style, Dedicated Style and Integrated Style. Reddin provides four highest levels of style in most appropriate way as - 1. Developer, 2. Bureaucrat, 3. Benevolent Autocrat and 4. Executive. Reddin also used four lowest levels of style in the most inappropriate way are like – Missionary, Deserter, Autocrat and Compromise.

Leader-Member Exchange Model: Leader-Member Exchange model is a relationship-based theory, focusing on the dyadic relationship to get the best from all team members. It's also known as 'Vertical Dyad Linkage Theory'. VDL model is used to create positive relationships between leader and members for increasing organizational success. This model offered three stages to develop relationship among them as- 1. Role Taking, 2. Role Making and 3. Routinization.

Approaches of Leadership

Approaches provides strategies to deal with phenomenon. There are some approaches to Leadership Style, as discussed below -

Trait Approach: The trait approach believes intellectual, physical and personality traits distinguish non-leaders from leaders, that minor variances exist between followers and leaders (Burns, 2003). Trait Theory suggests that effective leaders are born. They are in their position because of their natural traits and unique abilities that cannot be learned or developed.

Transformational Approach: Transformational leadership approach was given by James V Downtown in 1973 and popularized by James Burns in 1978. According to Bass and Riggio (2006), "The transformational leadership style achieves

high leadership performance and can exceed expectancies because it focuses not only on leadership performance but also on the human factors and the development of workers." Transformational leaders encourage and motivate the followers to catalyse changes that will help to grow and shape the unborn success of the institution. Transformation leaders believe in transforming the qualities of their followers. They inspire followers to attain higher-order needs like self-actualization, and self-esteem (Bass, 1985) and are influential in surging followers' motivation in the direction of self-sacrifice and achievement of organizational goals over personal interests (Bass,1995). The following are some components of the Transformational Approach:

I. Idealized Influence: Transformational leaders inspire their followers to take the leader as a role model. Charismatic leadership is an alternate term of idealized influence (Yuki, 1999; Shamir et al., 1993).

II. Inspirational Motivation: Leaders with inspirational motivation induce vision and mission for group and work with their team to achieve their goal. The leaders using this behaviour set high standards for followers besides communicating their vision in unambiguous ways and encouraging them to develop beyond the normal situations for their own and organizational growth (House and Shamir, 1993).

III. Intellectual Stimulation: Transformational leaders intellectually stimulate their followers and rationally deal with complex problems. This leadership approach builds organizational proficiency as well as character, similar to caring leadership behaviours (House and Shamir, 1993).

IV. Individualized Consideration: Transformational leaders display their concern for worker's needs and consider individual differences in work place.

Transaction Approach: The transactional leadership was rendered as in which leader-follower associations were grounded upon a series of agreements between followers and leaders (House & Shamir, 1993). Bass and Avolio (1994) observed transactional leadership "as a type of contingent-

reward leadership that have active and positive exchange between leaders and followers whereby followers were rewarded or recognized for accomplishing agreed upon objectives". Transactional leaders are less attracted to subordinates solely for non-giving rewards what they achieve, focus on mistakes to avoid intervenes until a normal development occurs (Howell & Avolio, 1993). This leadership approach varies time to time, situation to situation such as high degree of precision, technical expertise, time-constraints, particularly in technological intensive environment. "This type of leadership does not inspire workers to achieve beyond expected outcomes, however, if target is achieved, that means the system has worked, everyone is satisfied, and the business continues as usual," (Bass & Avolio, 2004).

Charismatic Approach: Charismatic leaders have charming or attractive qualities. These leaders are supportive to their followers, they are self-motivated, emotionally intelligent, and have self-awareness with positivity, empathy, courage and creativity. It shares multiple characteristics with Transformational Approach. That's you it's also called Transformation leadership style.

Different Leadership Styles

Leadership is a set behaviour or quality of a person or leader to influence or guide others. Each leader uses different style in their qualitative action to guide their followers. Some common styles are:

Democratic Leadership Style: Tannenbaum and Schmidt (2012) have defined democratic leadership as the leadership in which the decision-making is decentralized and is shared by all the subordinates. In the democratic leadership style, the poor decision making, potential for weak execution is high. Another big challenge associated with this leadership is the assumption that everyone has an equal stake in the decision-making with a shared level of expertise (Rukmani, et al., 2010). However, this style is also known to motivate the workers to perform better and also their views and opinions are given valued. The study by Elenkov (2002) indicated that the democratic

leadership has a positive impact on organizational performance. The democratic leadership gives freedom to the employees to make decisions along with their manager. In this type of leadership style, praises and criticism are given objectively and a sense of responsibility is developed among their employees (Elenkov, 2002). Bhargavi and Yaseen (2016) also analysed the impact of democratic leadership on organizational performance and as per their findings, democratic leadership positively affects the performance of the organization as it provides opportunities to the employees to express and implement their creative ideas and take part in the decision-making process. Choi (2007) also stated that a democratic leader is the one who focuses on the group discussion and group participation and as a result it positively influences the performance of the followers. So that it can be used for enriching the organizational performance as well as the efficiency.

Autocratic Leadership Style: Autocratic leaders are classic and bossy in nature. The autocratic leaders want their underlings to work according to them. Typically, autocratic leaders retain decision-making rights with them (Obiwuru, et al., 2011). This type of leaders forces their followers to execute the services and strategies according to the narrow way. Iqbal, Anwar, and Haider (2015) conducted a study to determine the impact of leadership styles on the organizational performance and stated that autocratic leadership is also referred as authoritarian leader. They are not much creative and only promote one-sided conversation which can severely affects the motivation and satisfaction level of the employees. This leader restricts the socialization and communication in workplace which is cordial for effective organizational performance. Bhargavi and Yaseen (2016) suggested that the autocratic leadership style has a positive impact on the organizational performance. This leadership style is more suitable when the schemes are to be completed within provided deadlines (Bhargavi & Yaseen, 2016).

Bureaucratic Leadership Style: Bureaucratic leaders force the people to follow the policies and procedures designed by them.

The leaders are explosively committed to their processes and procedures but not to their people. This technique is not very effective as it does not lead to the development and motivation of the employees. These leaders just focus on their tasks being completed in a systematic manner (Germano, 2010). Ojukuku et al. (2012) also stated that bureaucratic leadership has a negative impact on organizational performance. According to them, leaders do not induce the worker to work in the expected manner which can lead to improve organizational performance (Ojukuku, et al., 2012). Sougui et al. (2015) also presented similar results which stated that the bureaucratic leadership style does not impact the employee as well as organizational performance significantly. This method is beneficial only when the tasks are to be done in longer time following a mentioned procedure (Sougui, et al., 2015).

Laissez-Faire Leadership Style: Laissez-faire leadership may be the best or the worst of leadership styles (Goodnight, 2011). Laissez-faire leaders renounce the responsibilities and avoid making decisions, they give complete freedom to team members to do their work and set their own deadlines. Laissez-faire leaders generally allow their subordinate the power to make decisions about their work (Chaudhry & Javed, 2012). They provide teams with resources and advice but do not get involved in teamwork. If the leader monitors performance and gives feedback to team members regularly this style can be an effective one. Laissez-faire leaders give autonomy to the team member, that they found a high degree of job satisfaction and can increase productivity also. It can affect the organization also if team members do not manage their time well or do not have the knowledge, skills, or motivation to do their work effectively. This type of leadership can also transpire when managers do not have sufficient control over their staff (Ololube, 2013).

Educational Leadership and Management

Process

Leadership is the process of influencing employees towards the achievement of organizational goals and

organizational excellence (Naylor, 1999). Outstanding leaders have an institution-wide vision. They have a vision for the ideal future, which is shared by everyone in the institution and informs all of the policies, priorities, plans and processes that are used in the day-to-day operations of the organization. Through words and instances, leaders in education inspire the whole system by effective influencing behaviours, thoughts, and feelings to those working within it, and ensuring their vision by creating a strategic alignment across the whole system (Peretomode, 1991). Leadership considers more than simply the bottom line and looks to the future. According to Bennis, a leader creates a compelling vision, climate of trust, creates meaning and healthy empowering atmosphere. They seek to establish the best educational policies and strategies, which involve the improvement of educational programs and executive services aimed at creating competent graduates capable of entering significant positions in society (Ololube, 2013). Wallace and Hoyle (2005) contend that a change in strategy from the existing orthodoxies of radical transformation encouraged by reform programs towards a more moderate approach is necessary for effective leadership and management of the educational system. In order to attain organizational goals, educational management procedures entail the planning and creation of such system that guarantee the application of policies, strategies and action plans throughout a collection of integrated practices.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In the 21st century, there is a great demand of active and energetic educational Leaders for making quality achievement in educational organization. Management has an essential role in growing and improving institutional culture. The present review study aims at to introduce suitable leadership style for effective educational management. The present study is also aimed at finding the significant relationship between effective leadership style and student scholarly achievement. It also provides an understanding and critical review of published literature to the readers.

METHODOLOGY

This study is an academic evaluation as the author used to review previous established findings related to the study, based on primarily gathered information. For data collection, secondary research has been done from various online journals and documents to achieve the objectives of current study.

LEADERSHIP STYLE IN EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

One of the major factors that determines whether an organization succeeds or fails is effective management system and its leadership style. Leadership is the process by which a leader directs and inspires others to achieve organizational goals. Bush, Tony. (2006) popularized six managerial models such as Formal, Collegial, Political, Subjective, Ambiguity and Cultural Model. Tony stated that collegial model is related to participative leadership style which helps to improve the effectiveness of organizational practices. Ebrahim Hasan Al Khajeh (2018) conducted a study to examine the 'Impact of Leadership Styles on Organizational Performance'. Here both the primary and secondary research are been conducted. The primary research has been done with the help survey questionnaire and secondary research has been done through the review of existing established literature related to the study. This study reveals that the charismatic, bureaucratic and transactional leadership styles have negative relationship with organizational performance as it doesn't offer opportunities and freedom to the members. But transformational, autocratic, and democratic leadership styles have a positive relationship with the organizational performance. It also suggests that organizations should use leadership style that enhance the capabilities and skills of group members. Very recently, Uzma Sarwar, Rameez Tariq et al. (2022), conducted research to study the impact of principals' leadership style on the performance of teachers at the college level with 300 college teachers sample via a random sampling technique. For collection of data, they used a self-administrated questionnaire (five-point Likert Scale). This study showed that the majority of college principal

practices democratic style of leadership (at a higher level), Laissez-faire leadership style (at a moderate level), and autocratic leadership style (at a low level) in their colleges. The study also revealed that when principals increase the application of democratic practices, it progresses teacher's performance as well. The results of this study which discovered a favourable correlation between college principal's leadership style and teachers' effectiveness, were summarized by Okumu (2006) and Nanson (2010). The result of this study supports those of Imhangbe et al. (2019) who similarly found that teacher's work performance was positively correlated with democratic leadership style. This study also found a strong statistically positive relationship between democratic leadership style and teacher performance as followed by autocratic style. Thus, the result suggests that principals should adjust the leadership style based on the level of teachers and should change with the specific situations in the organization, which were also summarized by Bush, Tony (2006).

Saleem et al. (2020) discovered that the directive leadership style, followed by the supporting and achievement-oriented leadership styles, had a significant impact on teacher job performance in schools. On the other hand, being a good predictor of teacher job performance, participative leadership was not thought to be a favourable one. Lee et al. (2019) also found a significant relationship between transformational leadership and higher levels of supervisory coaching and performance feedback. These job resources act as a mediator between these variables and work engagement. Additionally, the findings demonstrated that work engagement modulates the associations between supervisory coaching and performance feedback to turnover intention. In general, Asian leaders can efficiently support various components of HRD through behaviours that are focused on growth and act as job resources to increase work engagement and boost to reduce turnover intention. Likewise, Akparep et al. (2019) conducted a study to know the influence of leadership style on organizational performance at TumaKavi Development Association. This investigation found that the TKDA operates primarily under democratic leadership. The organization's performance and its

operations have been greatly influenced by the democratic leadership style that is being employed. The findings of this study also showed a high correlation between TKDA organizational performance and leadership style. The study also depicts that the leader occasionally uses other leadership ideologies such as authoritarian and laissez-faire, whenever required to reach their purposes, The study also recommended other leadership styles in transforming the workplace as necessary.

EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP STYLE AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS

In a study, Ogbonnaya, C.N, et al. (2020) investigated the impact of transformational leadership style on students' academic achievement in English language with 18 Principals and 1, 267 SS2 students using 'Transformational leadership style Questionnaire' developed by Leithwood and Jantzi (1999) and 'English language Achievement Test (ELAT)'. This study discovered that Idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration under the dimensions of transformational leadership. This style has a positive relationship with student's academic achievement. The study showed that whenever the school Principals employed transformational leadership style, it gives direct and positive response to the students and teachers performance. The results of this study also correlate those of Azam and Natyada's (2012) study, which was done in South Thailand's private religious schools and found a positive link between academic achievement and transformational leadership. The results of Kappen's (2010) study also demonstrates both intrinsic motivation and transformational leadership have a favourable impact on students' motivation in achievement. Thus, the study suggests that educational leaders need to give importance on adopting transformational leadership style as a modern management style for the institution. Naz, F.; Rashid, S. (2021) presented a study to investigate the impact of instructional leadership on teachers' motivation level and students learning outcomes with 400 teachers from both public and private secondary schools. This study reveals that instructional leaders

encourage to promote teamwork, school climate, good relationship between parents and school, those who are responsible for giving quality education. Both the male and female personnel from private and public schools agreed that instructional leaders boost teacher's morale and believe in their potential which motivates the teachers more. The concept of Hayes model 4 also demonstrates that instructional leaders can affect student learning outcomes through teacher motivation. For making an effective educational environment instructional leadership is very important (Mannan, Sharma, Hoque, & Veeriah, 2017). This study also discovered that instructional leaders are responsible for providing quality education at secondary level as they have a massive influence on the teaching-learning process in schools. Furthermore, Day, Christopher. et al. (2016) studied on how a successful school leader applies transformational and instructional strategies in various phases to make educational culture different in shaping student outcomes. This study provides empirical evidence on the impact of leadership on student outcomes. The result shows that both transformational and instructional leadership are important for quantitative and qualitative improvement of different aspects and actions over time. Gerbi (2021), Jay (2014), and Fatana (2021), also found the leadership style of a school teacher is positively related to their performance that influence student's academic excellence as well. In another study, Dahar, A. M; Faize, A. F; Niwaz, A.; Hussain, A. M.; Zaman, A. (2010) found leadership styles and investigated its impact on academic achievement at the stage of secondary level in Punjab, Pakistan. This study depicted that academic success of science students are positively and significantly impacted by both democratic and autocratic leadership styles rather than laissez-faire leadership style. This study also reveals that democratic leadership style has a significant impact on the academic achievements of Arts students. Additionally, laissez-faire leadership style has a negligible and detrimental effects on it. The study discovered that a leader's leadership style effectively affects the educational process and results in academic achievement which is also claimed by Valesky et al. (1992) that a democratic leadership style results in a better school atmosphere (as a measure of academic achievement)

than an authoritarian or laissez-faire leadership style. The analysis of this study is consistent with those of Un-Nisa (2003), who found that leadership styles have a significant impact on the dependent variables of leader acceptance, job expectations, and six facets of job satisfaction, which are good influencers of academic achievement. This investigation backs up Waters, Marzano, and McNulty (2003) where they contend that there is a significant connection between good leadership and academic success. However, this study also supports Iqbal's (2005) conclusion that democratic style has greater impact than the authoritative style in case of female head teachers also.

In the last year, Stavros, K.; Stavroula, Savvidou. (2022) studied the role of management in educational organizations for optimizing the quality of education with the help of online survey questionnaire and found that when education is handled properly and schools are updated in a country, student performance increases and the education provided, is relevant and of high quality. This study also found that important aspects of educational administration including adequate planning, improving the school atmosphere, effective leadership, and teacher honours and praise for improving quality education. According to the conclusion of this study, management has an essential role in improving teaching and learning quality, consequently in improving educational quality. Similarly, Nancy et al. (2015) examines the relationship between transformational leadership and school climate, student mathematics and reading achievement in elementary schools. The findings of this study revealed a link between transformational leadership and school climate. However, no link was discovered between transformational leadership and student success, nor between school climate and student achievement. This is in accordance with the results reported by Heck and Hallinger (1996, 2005), Finnigan and Stewart (2009), Jacobson et al. (2005), Mulford et al. (2008), and Murakami-Ramvalho et al. (2010) that a principal's Transformational leadership attributes have no direct influence on student achievement. However, prior study (Braughton & Riley, 1991; Finnigan & Stewart, 2009; Hallinger & Heck, 1996; Robinson

et al., 2008) has proven that leadership, particularly transformational leadership, has an indirect influence on pupil achievement. Contrary to this, Silva et al. (2011) also observed that principal who joined in discussions with students about their prospective reading achievement can fulfil their specific target goal. This shows that principals who display the abilities required to be effective readers and foster the development of critical thinking skills, create a good example for their pupils which may influence their level of reading achievement. As previous research (Braughton & Riley, 1991; Finnigan & Stewart, 2009; Hallinger & Heck, 1996; Robinson et al., 2008) has reported that when a leader shows trust in teacher's abilities and encourages the development of novel techniques for teaching, reading achievement can be influenced even it is indirectly also.

DISCUSSION

Quality education depends on a quality curriculum and on the effective management system of an organization. In an educational organization principal performs most of the managerial activities including planning, organizing, supervising etc. Management has an important role in improving quality teaching, learning process for academic excellence. In the words of Mirkamali (1995, Management is the vital factor for developing both the organization and students' academic performance. Everyone keeps on saying that educational leadership has an immense importance since the early years of 21st century because of its effectiveness in educational institutions. Among many experts, Western (2013) describes leadership as a 'capability and practical experience of a person or a group to lead, to influence or to provide guidance to others or to the whole organization'. This evaluation tries to introduce a suitable leadership style for productive management system in promoting higher academic achievement. The study depicts that transformational, participative and democratic leadership style have a positive relationship with organization and its performance as it provides opportunities, discipline, freedom to the subordinates. Transformational democratic leadership has higher level of idealized influence and

inspirational motivation which modulates work engagement, performance, feedback and reduce turnover intention also. It also gives intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration that can increase job satisfaction among teachers or employees. This study also found some literature supported to laissez-faire style as an imperfect and Autocratic style with slightly significant for the purpose.

The teacher is the heart of classroom learning. Teachers with good leadership style provides quality teaching in classroom which promotes students' academic excellence. Believing in teachers potentials make them highly dedicated to work and always ready to teach their students, as it increases teacher's motivation and helps to retain them for longer periods. So, principal should encourage and motivate their staff and workers. Educational leaders need to believe in lifetime learning and should inculcate the sentiment of never-ending learning in teachers to create more productive and dynamic students in the classroom. Day, C. (2016) also provides empirical evidence that the schools' ability to promote and sustain effectiveness for long time is the result of leaders understanding and organizing school's need for an application through which teaching, learning culture, School climate, quality progression can be gained. Thus, educational administration should include adequate measures to improve school atmosphere, effective leadership style, teachers' recognition as an important aspect of quality teaching and learning and should try to change the school climate according to the new trends. Every workplace has distinctive resources and diverse climate and leaders should adopt leadership style based on them. Bush, Tony (2006) also states that manager

should utilize their style according to the diverse nature of educational context rather than adopting a 'one size fits all' style. This study shows that majority of school principal practices democratic leadership style at a higher level, which encourages the performance of teachers, and autocratic, laissez-faire leadership at lower level. But the organization should use that leadership style which enhance capacities and unique abilities of followers, educational manager should also adjust their leadership based on the level of workers and also on the specific situations of institution. Therefore, principal can use transformation democratic and participating leadership style to optimize the performance of teachers and to achieve higher academic excellence. The study also suggests that educational manager should encourage the staff to participate in their administrative activities and decision making.

CONCLUSION

Leadership style has an impact on the educational process in terms of effective management and academic achievements. It is stated that the 'Transformational-democratic leadership style' is the most productive and a significant resource input that has a favourable effect on academic accomplishment. Furthermore, it is determined that a laissez-faire leadership style has an adverse effect on student achievement. One must use leadership style in management process based on the situation and the level of subordinates. It can be concluded that suitable leadership style makes oneself natural leader to influence the followers in making progressive and efficient management system. It is also stated that if leadership styles are utilized well, they may become a significant predictor of academic accomplishment.

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